

Influence of Cooperative Activities on Micro-Business Financing in Ogoja Local Government Area of Cross River State.

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Abstract

This study focused on investigating the influence of cooperative activities on micro-business financing in Ogoja Local Government Area(LGA) of Cross River State. Micro-enterprise is generally referred to as a small business employing nine people or fewer, and having a balance sheet or turnover of not more than N5million while micro-business financing encompasses all means of raising of funds required to run these kind of business. Cooperative societies are an autonomous association of persons, united voluntarily to meet their common economic, social and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise. Cooperatives as business enterprise facilitates micro-business financing via; access to convenient, cheap, affordable, flexible and fitting loan with minimal administrative inconveniences. The specific objective of the study is to assess various cooperative activities as affecting micro-business financing in Ogoja LGA. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The sample size of 150 was determined through Taro Yamani formula. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools. Findings show that Cooperatives have contributed significantly to micro business financing in the area studied ($t=6.319$; $p=0.03$). It is therefore, recommended that individuals who intend to start micro businesses are encouraged to join cooperatives because membership of cooperative will assist them to overcome entry barriers as well as give them access to funding, business support services and formalization.

Keywords: Cooperative Societies, Cooperative Activities, Micro-Business, Business Financing.

Introduction

Generally, a micro-enterprise is defined as a small business employing less than nine people and having a turnover or balance sheet less than a certain amount. According to SMEDAN, Micro enterprises are defined as any enterprise employing between one to nine people and running on a capital base from one naira to ₦5 million excluding cost of land. Women own majority of these micro

enterprise. Women entrepreneurial activities go beyond a means for economic survival but also have positive social repercussions for the women themselves and their social environment (UNIDO, 2001). In the informal sector where they are common, they are majorly into value added activities and business value chains such agricultural processing, art, business intermediation, extractive industries and in the service sector. Micro businesses are seen by many as a viable option for dealing with multifaceted challenges facing Nigeria. Since the last two decades, many people have entered the field of entrepreneurship in greatly increasing numbers. According to Aderemi et al., (2008), knowing that managing and creating business in environment like Nigeria is quite cumbersome; majority of them joined cooperatives as strategy for taking leadership roles in business and in dealing with obstacles in their businesses. Majority of these enterprises formed are micro businesses owing to lack of resources.

A cooperative is “an autonomous association of persons, united voluntarily to meet their common economic, social and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise” (ICA, 1995 and ILO, 2002). This study defines cooperative as a form of association in which a group of individuals who have joint interest mutually agree to come together to promote their interest in the area of economic activities such as production, distribution or marketing of goods and services as well as provision of other welfare benefits to their members. With these activities, cooperatives are able to alleviate poverty, particularly in developing countries where a high level of poverty prevails. In Nigeria, it is reported that about 70% of the population estimated at 156.05 million by Global Finance (2011) is still living in abject poverty (Oshewolo, 2010). Global Finance (2011) reported that 83.91 percent of the Nigerian population is living on less than US\$2 a day and that the inequality of wealth distribution is 42.9 percent.

Consequently; poverty, unfriendly business environment, income inequality and unemployment are among the peculiar challenge facing the Nigerian economy. One of the challenges of developing countries is finding successful solution to poverty and economic underdevelopment (Gunga, 2008). Hence, the need to investigate Cooperative Activities as it affects Micro Business Financing in the study area.

Objectives of the Study

The central objective of this study is to investigate the influence of cooperative activities on micro-business financing in Ogoja Local Government Area of Cross-River State.

Research Question

1. To what extent has cooperative activities contributed to micro business financing?

Hypothesis of the Study

1. Ho₁: Cooperative activities have not contributed significantly to micro business financing in the study area.

Literature Review

According to SMEDAN, Micro enterprises are defined as any **enterprise** employing between one to nine people and having a capital base from one naira to ₦5 million excluding cost of land. The role of micro enterprise in the national economy cannot be underestimated. These enterprises are being given increasing policy attention in recent years, particularly in third world countries partly because of growing disappointment with results of development strategies focusing on large scale capital intensive and high import dependent industrial plants. The impact of micro enterprises is felt in greater utilization of local raw materials, employment generation, encouragement of rural development, development of entrepreneurship, mobilization of local savings, linkages with bigger industries, provision of regional balance by spreading investments more evenly, provision of avenue for self-employment and provision of opportunity for training managers and semi-skilled workers. The vast majority of developed and developing countries rely on dynamism, resourcefulness and risk tasking of micro enterprises to trigger and sustain process of economic growth.

In Nigeria, the Third National Development plan (2010) defines micro business as a manufacturing or service organization whose employee is not more than 10. Obafemi (2001) defines it as one whose total assets or capital is less than \$10,000 and employee fewer than 10 full time workers”.

Meanwhile, a study by the Federal Office of Statistic (2001) shows that 70% of all business in Nigeria employ less than 10 employees. Going by this definition of Micro businesses is an umbrella term for firms with less than 10 employees. The micro business subsector provides an average of 50% of Nigeria’s employment, and 50% of its industrial output (Ariyo, 2005). In his own contribution to the definition of the subject matter, Birch (1970) argued that small firms are essential in job creation.

Concept of Cooperative

Abia (2000) defined cooperative as self-help organisation formed by either producers or consumers of goods and services usually by initiative ideas of one or two people who plays advocacy role and enlist other people to the cooperative. According to Owojori and Oladejo (2009) Cooperative society is one

among other institutions that promote industrialization and entrepreneurship desirable for economic development. Epetimehin (2006) described cooperatives as a business owned and controlled by the people who use its service. They operate and finance the business or service for their mutual benefit. Roy (1964) saw cooperatives as voluntary organisation established for the pursuance of social, economic and political interest of members. The International Labour Organisation (ILO) in its studies and report series, No 57 of 1960 on cooperative management and administration viewed cooperatives as an association of person usually of limited means, who have voluntarily joined together to achieve a common economic end through the formation of a democratically controlled business organisation, making equitable accepting a fair share of the risk and benefit of the undertaking. Onuoha (1986) saw cooperatives as businesses of patrons whose motive is to obtain the goods and services they involve at a cost through their combined undertakings. The International Cooperative Alliance (ICA) which is the world apex body of cooperative movements at its centennial congress and General Assembly in Manchester, 1995, defines cooperative as ‘an autonomous association of persons united voluntarily to meet their common economic, social, and cultural needs and aspirations through a jointly-owned and democratically-controlled enterprise.’

Contributions of Cooperative to Micro business development

The contributions of effective cooperatives to economic growth and development processes cannot be overemphasized, particularly in low income countries like Nigeria, where a large number of the citizens still live below US\$1 per day.

Micro business Financing

Cooperatives encourage their members to form the habit of saving without being extravagant. They mobilize savings and pool available resources from the members, utilize the same in the best possible manner and share the benefits among members. Consequently, they can be setup in poor communities, where access to savings and credit at non-exploitative terms is of greatest importance (Adekunle and Henson, 2007). UK Aid reiterates that cooperatives enable poor people to access financial services, credits, as well as insurance and remittances, which go a long way to reduce vulnerability since the poor could accrue savings, own assets and smooth out consumption by virtue of their participation in the association. In Nigeria, the credit and thrift cooperative has been a major avenue for the working class to save part of their incomes because such savings are deducted directly at source, and this seems more convenient than bank savings that attract virtually 0% interest.

The stringent conditions attached to loan by formal financial institutions and the inability of funds made available by existing banks to reach the poor segment of the population have increased the relevance of the informal financial institutions (Yusuf and Ijaiya, 2009). This underscores the relevance of cooperatives in the provision of funds to members at affordable and low interest rate. Elhiraika (1999) has noted that lending by traditional formal financial institutions to small borrowers in developing countries is often limited due to collateral requirement and high interest rates. Cooperatives assist their members financially by providing loans at low interest rate for start-up capital or for business expansion thereby promoting entrepreneurial activities. The interest rate charged by them is usually lower compared to what obtains in the formal financial institutions. Since members do not require any collateral securities to access loans, (it is assumed that a member's shareholding is his/her collateral) loan procurement is made easier and almost stress free. The staff cooperatives in most organisations are formed to bridge this gap and help members have access to credit, which enable them to acquire the basic necessities of life and to improve their standard of living (Azeez, 2011), to start a business, pay medical bills, further their education or sponsor education of their children (Wanyama, Develtere and Pollet, 2008).

Empirical Studies

In a study on mobilization of rural savings role of cooperatives and business financing in Southwest, Nigeria, Osuntogun and Adeyemo (2001) examine the interrelationships between the value of members savings in the group and extent of business finance received. Using Pearson correlation matrix they found that, the larger the membership strength of the group, the higher would be the number of members striving hand to make their savings, which invariably increase the capital base of the societies. They also observed that there is a positive correlation between the value of members' savings and access to other financing opportunities.

In another development, Adeyemo and Bamire (2005) examine the saving and investment patterns of cooperative and non-cooperative farmers in South-western Nigeria. With four hundred respondents, using regression analysis, the study shows that cooperative farmers have higher annual total investment than non-cooperative farmers.

Ahmad (2005) adopts the use of time series approach in examining the role of cooperative societies in micro business development. He observed that for over 160 years, cooperative have been an effective way for people to exert control over their economic livelihood as they play an increasingly important

role in facilitating job creation, economic growth and social development. He observed that cooperative membership influence choice of business, funding option and choice of inputs sources used.

In a study by Saka, Lawal, Abee, Balogun and Oyegbami (2008), on the effect of group participation on access to micro-credit among rural women in Osun and Oyo states, using data from 380 respondents, it was observed that 85.6% of rural women belonged to micro credit group through which 82.3% were able to source credit. They observed that cooperative societies granted higher volume of credit than the local groups while women farmers had access to greater volume of credit than women traders, and that micro credit have significant impact on economic status of the women.

Otto and Ukpere (2011) carried out an empirical study on the contributions of cooperatives societies in Nigeria as a potential source of capital formation and employment. Using t-test on data from 282 respondents, the work identified cooperative credits and thrift associations as a veritable source of capital formation which is required for investment purposes. It further explained that the thrift cooperative as a micro finance agency is also a direct source of employment for those engaged in its management or coordination. The scope of operation of a cooperative society is based on the size of its capital and membership

Abia (2000) agreed that cooperative is the bedrock of capital formation for business financing in Nigeria. He studied the role of cooperative in small business development using regression analysis . Their conclusion is that cooperatives builds competitive strength of businesses and assist members to receive timely help and resources that they could not get individually.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on the Michael Porter generic competitive strategies framework developed in 1986. A firm gains competitive advantage when it can perform chains of business activities cheaply or better than its competitors. Competitive strategy grows out of the value a firm is able to create from its buyers that exceed the cost of creating it (Tarnwa, 2013). Generic strategies help organizations to cope with the five competitive forces in the industry: bargaining power of suppliers, threat of substitute, bargaining power of buyers and threat of new entrants. According to Porter (1996), there are three generic competitive strategies: cost leadership, differentiation and focus. A firm that pursues cost leadership strategy produces standardized products and uses economies of scale, experience curve effect and a large customer base to achieve low cost; lower than the industry average. This is possible when there is tight cost control, when there is access to cheap capital, when there is close supervision

of labor that lead to easy manufacturing. Differentiation strategy focuses on creating product that is unique in the industry; using brand name, design, features, customer service and network to generate advantage in the market place. Firms that pursue differentiation strategy selects one or more product attributes considered as important and positions itself to meeting the demands of the attributes. Focus strategy entails choosing a narrow competitive scope within the industry and positioning on serving the chosen segment to the exclusion of other market segment. In this strategy, energy is focused on a niche and market mix is designed to meet the needs of such narrow market segment. The focus is on effectively serving the selected market and not on efficiency. Many authors believed that it is difficult to achieve both cost leadership and differentiation at the same time. However, membership of cooperatives seems to have enabled college startups to gain competitive advantage in the market place in the three dimensions.

This theory is relevant in this study because it x-rays how cooperatives play increasing role in achieving cost leadership, product differentiation and niche maximization for micro enterprises. Literature is filled with evidence that cooperatives assist members to build competitive advantage in the market place.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

The researcher adopted a descriptive survey research method.

Area of study

The area of study is Ogoja Local Government Area of Cross River State. The Latitude is 6.6584, while the Longitude is 8.7992. The population according to 2006 census is 171,901. It consists of many towns like Uhmuria, Igoli, Odajie, Adagum and Ekajuk. Their major source of livelihood is subsistence agriculture, basically farming of cassava, yams, palm oil, palm wine etc.

Population of the Study

Population of the study consist of all members of cooperatives societies in Ogoja Local Government Area who established and run micro business enterprises. According to the Divisional Cooperative officer in the area, there are 271 registered cooperatives but only 81 are functional. These 81 cooperative societies have membership strength of 1,488. This number constitutes the population of the study.

Sample Size Determination and Sampling Procedure

Multi stage sampling was adopted in this study despite that cooperative members that have micro business that have existed for at least two years were given equal chance of being included in the sample. In the first stage, functional cooperatives that exist in the area of study were selected. Out of the 271 registered cooperatives, only 81 who were functional were selected. In stage two, two cooperatives were selected from each of the communities in the area of study. In stage three, members of cooperatives in these selected cooperatives who have micro businesses that have existed for at least two years were selected.

Table 1: Showing how the sampling was done

Towns	No of selected cooperatives	No of members	No, of sampled respondents
Uhmuria	2	36	26
Igoli	2	41	36
Odajie	2	29	23
Adagun	2	52	42
Ekajuk	2	43	23
Total	10	201	150

Taro Yamani formula was used to determine the sample size of the study as seen in the Table

The formula is stated as

$$n = N / 1 + N (e^2)$$

where;

n = desired sample size

N = Population of the study

e= acceptable error limit (5% is proposed)

Substituting the formula

$$= 240 / 1 + 240(0.05)^2$$

$$= 240 / 1 + (240 \times 0.0025)$$

$$n = 150$$

Data Analysis

Both Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in achieving the objectives of the study. Frequency distribution, percentages and mean score rating were used to achieve objective the research questions.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Socio-Economic Characteristics of the respondents

Data collected were presented and analyzed. Research questions and hypothesis were respectively answered and tested based on the data collected.

Table 2: Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents studied

No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Sex of the Respondents		
	Male	65	43
	Female	85	57
	Total	150	100.00
2.	Age of the respondents		
	Less than 25	08	5
	26- 40	44	29
	41-65	69	47
	Above 65	29	19
	Total	150	100.00
3.	Marital status		
	Single	24	16
	Married	110	73
	Widowed/divorced	16	11
	Total	150	100
4.	Type of business		
	Manufacturing/Extractive	64	43
	Processing	51	34

	Services	35	23
	Total	150	100
5.	Educational qualification		
	No formal education	19	13
	Primary	28	18
	Secondary	73	49
	Tertiary	30	20
	Total	150	100.00
7	Cooperative membership		
	0-5 years	55	37
	6-10years	42	28
	11-15years	34	22
	Above 15 years	19	13
	Total	150	100
8	Status of business		
	Registered	104	69
	Not registered	46	31
	Total	150	100
9	Major source of fund for business assets		
	a. cooperative	74	49
	b. Bank	04	2
	C. Local lender	29	19
	d. Self, family and friends	43	29
	Total	150	100

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Table 2 revealed that 43% of the respondents were male and 57% female. Thirty-three percent age less than forty while 67% aged above 40 years. Sixteen percent were single while the rest were either married or widowed. Forty-three percent were into manufacturing, 34% were into processing and 23% operate in the service sector. Thirteen percent of the respondents did not attend any formal education while only 18% had only primary education. Forty-nine percent had secondary education while only 2% attempted tertiary education.

Thirty-seven percent have been in cooperative for less than 5 years where 13% had been in cooperative for over 15 years. About 50% of the respondents have been in cooperative between 6-15 years. Sixty-nine percent of the micro-businesses studied was registered while 31% had not been registered. In the same way, major source of funding for the business came from cooperatives (49%) and self/family.

Table 3: Extent to which cooperative activities contribute to micro business financing

	Frequency	Mean	Remark
Provision of access to loan	150	4.0	Accepted
Provision of convenient loan opportunity	150	3.90	Accepted
Provision of cheap and affordable loan	150	3.30	Rejected
Provision of loan that's flexible and fitting according to season	150	2.58	Rejected
Provision of loan opportunities with favorable terms and conditions	150	4.29	Accepted
Provision of loan with minimal administrative inconveniences	150	2.81	Rejected
Training/monitoring on loan use	150	3.71	Accepted
Affordable or no collateral	150	3.61	Accepted
Access to donor/government aids	150	4.56	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Table 3 showed that cooperatives have contributed significantly to micro business by provision of access to loans, provision of convenient loan opportunity with favourable terms and conditions. They also offer training on loan use, making loans affordable without collateral as well as provision of access to donor/government aids.

Test of hypothesis One

Ho1: Cooperatives have not contributed significantly to micro business financing

Table 4 One-Sample Test Showing whether cooperative have contributed significantly to micro business financing

		Test Value = 0				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Lower	Upper
Micro business financing		6.319	149	.030	0.7533	1.2112	3.754

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Since the calculated t-value is higher than the table t-value and p-value is significant, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore we conclude that cooperatives have contributed significantly to micro business financing.

Discussion of Findings

There is increasing number of businesses that have registered formally owing to membership of cooperatives. The profile of micro businesses studied revealed that about 80% of their businesses were funded by cooperatives and self. About 50% of funding for business asset came from cooperatives. These findings affirmed the discovery made in Omotosho (2007) who stated that cooperatives provide access to funding for business owners. The study revealed that cooperatives do not only provide funding for businesses but also serve as guarantor for members who got financing elsewhere. They also provide information on reliability of suppliers, price, discount and quality. In circumstances where cooperatives cannot provide the fund directly, they provide platform for saving up the money or surety them for lease agreement. They also offer training/monitoring on loan uses.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

Cooperatives have contributed significantly to micro business financing in the area studied ($t= 6.319$; $p=0.03$). Cooperatives contribute to micro business financing by providing access to loans and creating opportunities for affordable and convenient credit without collateral or stringent terms. They also provide training/monitoring on loan use as well as access to donor/government aids. This is in line

with the findings of Otaokpukpu, Ogbu, and Okonkwo (2017) stating that member participation has significant influence on cooperative financial performance

Conclusion

There is concrete evidence that cooperative societies play significant role in micro business development. The services they render assist member to overcome constraints inherent in starting and running micro businesses.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings made in the study

Individuals who intend to start micro businesses are encouraged to join cooperatives because membership of cooperative will assist them to overcome entry barriers as well as give them access to funding, business support services and formalization.

References

- Abia (2000). 'Rural cooperatives Societies and the Transformation of the Lower Cross River Region' *Kiabara*, 6(1),
- Adekunle, B. and Henson, S.J. (2007). The Effect of Cooperative Thrift and Credit Societies on Personal Agency Belief: A Study of Entrepreneurs in Osun State, Nigeria' *African Journal of Agricultural Research*. Vol 2 (12) pp. 678-686.
- Adeyemo, R and Bamire, A. S (2005) Saving and Investment Patterns of Cooperative Farmers in South western Nigeria. *Journal of Social Science* 11(3) pp. 183-192.
- Ahmad Bello (2005). The Role of Cooperative Societies in Economic Development, Munich Personal RePEc Archive
- Azeez, O. (2011) Building Wealth through Cooperative Societies' <http://www.thisdaylive.com/articles/building-wealth-through-cooperative-societies/103583/> [accessed 12 February 2012].
- Elhiraika, A.B. (1999) The Growth and Potential of Savings and Credit Cooperative Societies in Swaziland' *Development Policy Review*. vol 17 pp. 355-374.
- Epetimehin (2006). *Understanding the Dynamics of Cooperatives*, Tadon Publishers, Ibadan.
- Global Finance (2011) Nigeria Country Report' [www. Gfmag.com/gdp-data-country-reports](http://www.Gfmag.com/gdp-data-country-reports) [accessed 22 December 2011].

- Gunga, O.S. (2008) The Cooperative Movement in Kenya and its Potential for Enhancement of ICT Livelihoods' www.esfim.org/wp-content/uploads/kenya-country [accessed 10 December 2011].
- International Cooperative Alliance (1995) Revision to the Cooperative Principles' <http://www.ica.coop/principles-revisions> [accessed 29 November 2011].
- International Labour Organization (2002) ILO Recommendation 93 on Cooperative Promotion' www.ilo.int/public/english/employment/ent/coop/africa [accessed 29 November 2011].
- www.ica.coop/europe/ra2000/speech
- Otaokpukpu, J.N., Ogbu, S.O. & Okonkwo, J.C. (2017). Effect of Type and Participation on Cooperative Financial Performance in Orumba South L.G.A of Anambra State. The (IIARD) International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research. Vol. 3 No. 8. 104 – 114.
- Otto, G. and Ukpere, W. (2011). Credit and thrift cooperative in Nigeria: A potential source of capital formation and employment. African Journal of Business Management , 5(14), 5675- 5680.
- Oshewolo, S. (2010) Galloping Poverty in Nigeria: An Appraisal of the Government Interventionist Policies' Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa .Vol 12, No.6 pp.264- 274.
- Owojori,A.A. and Oladejo, M. (2009):Re-engineering cooperative societies for sustainable small and medium business growth and development in Nigeria. [http://www.thefreelibrary.com/Business,international community](http://www.thefreelibrary.com/Business,international+community).
- Roy (1964). Cooperative Today and Tomorrow, Geneva.
- Saka J. O., Lawal B.O., Abeeb W., Balogun O.L, Oyegbami A.,(2008) Effect of group participation on access to micro credit among rural women in Osun and Oyo states, Nigeria. Journal of Agriculture Extension Vol. 12(1)
- Yusuf, N., Ijaiya, G. T. and Ijaiya, M. A. (2009) Informal Financial Institutions and Poverty Reduction in the Informal Sector of Offa Town, Kwara State: A Case Study of Rotating Savings and Credit Associations (ROSCAs)' Journal of Social Sciences. 20(1) pp. 71-81.